

Measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ Cross Section in the Energy Range $\sqrt{s} = 760 - 798$ MeV with CMD-3 Detector Based on Data from the Tracking System and Its Contribution to the Muon ($g - 2$) Hadronic Term

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The cross section of the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ has been measured with the Cryogenic Magnetic Detector (CMD-3) at the electron-positron collider VEPP-2000. The measurement is based on data samples that were collected in the center-of-mass energy range $\sqrt{s} = 760 - 798$ MeV corresponding to an integrated luminosity of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = 18.4 \text{ pb}^{-1}$, covering the kinematic region of the $\omega(782)$ isoscalar resonance. The total systematic uncertainty of the cross section measurement is about 2%, dominated by the luminosity determination uncertainty of 1.5%. The results are compared with the previous most precise measurements from experiments. The measured cross section is used to evaluate the leading-order hadronic vacuum polarization contribution of the 3π channel to the muon anomalous magnetic moment ($a_\mu^{3\pi}$).

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1. Introduction

The Standard Model (SM) successfully describes most experimental observations in elementary particle physics [1]. While the early 1970s marked the birth of the SM, the 1980s began the era of experimental validation of its predictions. The discovery of the weak intermediate vector bosons W^\pm and Z [2] at the Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS) in 1983 confirmed the electroweak theory and solidified the SM's foundation. The culmination of this experimental verification came in 2012 with the discovery of the Higgs boson [3, 4] at the Large

Hadron Collider (LHC), completing the predicted SM particle spectrum.

Despite its remarkable success, the SM remains manifestly incomplete as it leaves many critical questions unanswered. It fails to explain dark matter, neutrino masses and the matter-antimatter asymmetry in the universe. This incompleteness has spurred the development of numerous models such as supersymmetric theories, Grand Unified Theories (GUTs), and extra-dimensional models, collectively referred to as physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM) or New Physics [5].

Precision measurements of the muon's anomalous magnetic moment (AMM or $a_\mu = (g - 2)/2$) represent one of the most sensitive tests of the SM. The Fermilab Muon $g - 2$ experiment initially reported a significant

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discrepancy between their measurement [6, 7] and SM prediction based on White Paper 2020 (WP20) [8] up to 5 standard deviations (σ), potentially signaling New Physics. Recent developments have significantly changed this picture. A key factor is the CMD-3 experiment measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ cross section [9] generally shows larger values than previous experiments, especially in the energy range \sqrt{s} from 600 MeV to 750 MeV where differences reach up to 5%. So far as this channel contributes approximately 73% of the hadronic production in e^+e^- annihilation, incorporating the CMD-3 data changes the 2π contribution to the hadronic part of the muon AMM, reducing the discrepancy to just one standard deviation [10].

This finding receives independent validation from lattice quantum chromodynamics (QCD) calculations. The leading-order hadronic vacuum polarization (LO HVP) contribution, now calculable with 0.9% precision, agrees closely with both the CMD-3 data and the experimental a_μ value [11]. The current precision of lattice QCD calculations represents a significant advancement, enabling a robust lattice-QCD average for the LO-HVP contribution [12].

The Muon $g - 2$ Theory Initiative's 2025 White Paper (WP25) [13] reflects these developments by adopting lattice QCD results for the LO HVP contribution. This marks a substantial shift from WP20 [8], which relied on data-driven dispersive approaches using $e^+e^- \rightarrow$ hadrons cross section measurements. The updated SM prediction now shows agreement with the current experimental average given in the final report of the muon E989 experiment [14].

Efforts continue to reconcile lattice QCD and dispersive methods for the LO HVP contribution, with WP25 omitting the latter due to unresolved tensions among experimental inputs. Resolving the tensions in data-driven estimations of the HVP contribution remains a critical priority. Additional experimental results, particularly in the ρ - ω resonance region, are essential for achieving this goal.

The VEPP-2000 collider plays a crucial role in resolving these tensions, as its energy range covers $\sim 91\%$ of the hadronic contributions to a_μ calculations. Its high-statistics data collected in the ρ - ω region promise significant improvements in the precision of hadronic cross section measurements.

The $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ channel represents the second-largest contribution to the muon AMM after $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$. Currently, the precision of the 3π contribution is limited to about 0.1 ppm due to discrepancies between experimental measurements [15–19]. Substantial tensions exist among the different experiments in the $\omega(782)$ peak region. The measurements from SND [15] and CMD-2 [16] show a significant discrepancy exceeding 8%. While BaBar did not perform a direct cross section measurement in this region, their analysis of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0\gamma$ process using Vector Meson Dominance (VMD) determined the cross section near the ω lies between the values reported by SND and CMD-2 and it shows closer agreement with the SND results within 3% [17]. BESIII measurements [18] also show better agreement with SND than CMD-2, though with larger uncertainties. The most recent Belle II measurements [19] are higher than the cross section observed by BaBar by more than 6%.

This paper presents results of the measuring cross section of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process in the energy region \sqrt{s} from 760 MeV to 798 MeV based on the total integrated luminosity of 18.4 pb^{-1} and involving high statistics of selected signal events $\sim 2.2 \cdot 10^6$.

2. CMD-3 detector and dataset

2.1. CMD-3 detector at VEPP-2000 collider

Currently, the Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences is running experiments at the VEPP-2000 electron-positron collider [20].

The VEPP-2000 collider covers a center-of-mass (c.m.) energy range from 320 to 2000 MeV with luminosity up to $10^{32} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. Two detectors, the Cryogenic Magnetic Detector (CMD-3) and the Spherical Neutral Detector (SND), are installed at the interaction regions of the collider. The main physical program is the precision measurement of exclusive hadronic and QED cross sections, the study of the dynamics of the production of multi-hadron states, and the physics of hadron interactions in the sector of light quarks. The CMD-3 is a general-purpose detector designed to measure the hadronic cross sections in the center-of-mass energy range below 2 GeV [21]. The general view of the CMD-3 detector is presented in Fig. 1. The CMD-3 detector consists of the cylindrical drift chamber (DC), placed inside a superconductive solenoid with a magnetic field of 1.3 T, and an electromagnetic calorimeter system. The DC and magnetic system combine to generate a magnetic spectrometer that measures the coordinates, angles, and momenta of charged particles. The outer muon system of the detector located outside the iron yoke is used to mark cosmic ray particles. The electromagnetic calorimeter, which detects neutral particles, consists of a barrel liquid xenon (LXe) calorimeter and an outer section made of cesium iodide (CsI) crystals. Additional details on the subsystems are available in dedicated references: the drift chamber is described in [22], the superconducting solenoid in [23], the electromagnetic calorimeter in [24], and the muon system in [25].

2.2. Dataset

This paper presents cross section measurements for the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process, based on data collected with the CMD-3 detector during two dedicated scans in 2018. The experimental strategy focused on the ω -meson resonance region, with measurements performed at discrete energy points across the center-of-mass (\sqrt{s}) range from 760 MeV to 798 MeV. Two scans were executed: the OMPHI2018 scan

FIG. 1: (Color online) The schematic layout of the Cryogenic Magnetic Detector (CMD-3): 1 - vacuum chamber, 2 - drift chamber, 3 - endcap BGO calorimeter, 4 - Z-chamber, 5 - superconducting solenoid, 6 - Liquid Xenon calorimeter, 7 - CsI calorimeter, 8 - yoke, 9 - VEPP-2000 focusing superconducting solenoid.

is optimized for ω -meson parameters, and the SCAN2018 scan is covered for a wider energy range.

As detailed in Section 3, event selection for $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ relied exclusively on drift chamber information. Consequently, the energy region $\sqrt{s} = 760 - 798 \text{ MeV}$ was selected, where the 3π cross section is dominated by ω resonance contributions and effective background suppression can be achieved without calorimeter system data. Within this energy window: OMPHI2018 provided 5 energy points with 14.5 pb^{-1} integrated luminosity (\mathcal{L}_{int}), and SCAN2018 contributed 22 energy points with $\mathcal{L}_{int} = 3.9 \text{ pb}^{-1}$ yielding a combined luminosity of 18.4 pb^{-1} for the $\omega(782)$ region.

3. Data Analysis

A precise examination of this channel is therefore essential for understanding the discrepancy between experimental measurements of the muon AMM and SM predictions. Two independent analysis strategies were developed in order to guarantee reliable results. The

approach presented in this work prioritizes high signal efficiency in the $\omega(782)$ -meson region while maintaining strong suppression of physical backgrounds. For this purpose, only charged pions (π^\pm) are fully reconstructed using track parameters of the particles traversing a drift chamber only. Neutral pions (π^0) are reconstructed exclusively for track efficiency determination only.

A second independent strategy, currently in progress, uses datasets with fully reconstructed three-pion events. This approach incorporates a kinematic fit to improve the resolution of charged-particle and photon parameters and further suppress background. Future comparison of results from both methods will enable cross-validation of systematic uncertainties.

3.1. Event Selection

The signal process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ is characterized by the following signature:

- Charged pions (π^\pm) produce two non-collinear oppositely charged tracks in the drift chamber originating from the interaction point.
- A neutral pion (π^0) decaying promptly into two photons ($\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$) that are detected as two separate clusters in the calorimeter system.

In the energy range below $\sqrt{s} < 1$ GeV, the dominant physical background processes are:

- $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-(\gamma)$,
- $e^+e^- \rightarrow e^+e^-(\gamma)$,
- $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-(\gamma)$.

These processes can produce two non-collinear oppositely charged tracks when accompanied by hard initial-state radiation (ISR). If an additional final-state radiation (FSR) photon (or any background photon) is present, such events may acquire the signature of 3π .

The acollinearity angle distribution of the background events in the azimuthal plane is $\Delta\phi = \pi - |\phi_1 - \phi_2|$, with a sharp peak close to $\Delta\phi = 0$ that markedly different from the signal distribution. This difference enables effective background suppression by rejecting events with small $\Delta\phi$ values.

Additional backgrounds arise from cosmic particles and beam-related interactions. Typically, these events have an origin point that is not associated with the beam interaction region.

Figure 2 shows a two-dimensional plot of simulated signal and background events within the kinematic region constrained by energy and momentum conservation. The vertical and horizontal axes represent $p_{\pi^+}/2E_{\text{beam}}$ versus $p_{\pi^-}/2E_{\text{beam}}$, respectively. Based on the event distributions, constraints on the range of allowable pion momenta (black dashed curve) that provide significant background suppression were determined.

FIG. 2: (Color online) Simulated signal and background events on the $p_{\pi^+}/2E_{\text{beam}}$ vs $p_{\pi^-}/2E_{\text{beam}}$ plot at $E_{\text{beam}} = 391.5$ MeV. Black points: $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ signal. Blue, red, and green points: $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$, $e^+e^- \rightarrow e^+e^-$, and $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events, respectively.

The $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ event candidates were selected from DC data using the following criteria:

1. Two oppositely charged tracks ($q_1+q_2=0$)
2. Minimum of 10 hits per track ($n_{\text{hits}} \geq 10$) for reliable trajectory reconstruction.
3. Fiducial volume requirement: polar angles θ_{π^\pm} within $[1, \pi - 1]$ rad.
4. Proximity to the interaction point:
 - Minimal track transverse distance to the beam axis: $\rho_{\pi^\pm} < 0.1$ cm,
 - Track Z-coordinate along the beam axis with respect to the center of the beams interaction point should be: $|z_{\pi^\pm}| < 10$ cm.
5. Acollinearity requirement: $\Delta\phi = |\pi - |\phi_{\pi^+} - \phi_{\pi^-}|| \geq 0.25$ rad
6. Momentum constraints:
 - Charged particle momentum:
 $90 < p_{\pi^\pm} < 111.9 + 1.126 \cdot E_{\text{beam}} \text{ MeV}/c$,
 - Transverse momentum requirement:
 $p_T^{\pi^\pm} > 50 \text{ MeV}/c$.
 - Average normalized momentum:
 $0.35 < \frac{(p_{\pi^+} + p_{\pi^-})}{2 \cdot E_{\text{beam}}} < 0.7$.
 - Invariant mass of two oppositely charged pions constraint: $M_{\pi^+\pi^-} < 1.66 \cdot E_{\text{beam}} \text{ MeV}/c^2$

Figures 3–7 show experimental and simulated distributions of the key parameters used for event selection in the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ analysis. The vertical dashed lines indicate the selection criteria applied to each parameter. The Y-axis represents normalized event count, calculated as events divided by the total number of events within the selection region.

The rejection of events with a small $\Delta\phi$ drastically reduces the background as shown in Fig. 8.

FIG. 3: (Color online) The polar angle θ distribution of charged pions from the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process. Black dots represent experimental data and the simulated signal events correspond to the red curve. The vertical dashed lines indicate the applied selection.

FIG. 4: (Color online) Event distribution along the beam axis versus the Z-coordinate of the track of charged pions from the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process. Black dots represent experimental data and the simulated signal events correspond to the red curve. The vertical dashed lines indicate the applied selection.

FIG. 5: (Color online) The number of drift hits per track N_{hit} of charged pions from the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process. Black dots represent experimental data and the simulated signal events correspond to the red curve. The vertical dashed line indicates the applied selection cut.

FIG. 7: (Color online) The distribution of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ events as a function of the acollinearity angle in the azimuthal plane. Black dots represent experimental data and the simulated signal events correspond to the red curve. The vertical dashed lines indicate the applied selection cuts.

FIG. 6: (Color online) The transverse distance ρ from the beam axis of tracks from the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process. Black dots represent experimental data and the simulated signal events correspond to the red curve. The vertical dashed line indicates the applied selection cut. Logarithmic scale.

FIG. 8: (Color online) The distribution shows background events as a function of the acollinearity angle $\Delta\phi$ in the azimuthal plane. The vertical dashed lines indicate the applied selection cuts. Logarithmic scale.

3.2. Detection efficiency

The detection efficiency is determined using Monte Carlo (MC) simulation as the ratio of true

3π events computed after and before applying the selection criteria,

$$\varepsilon_{3\pi} = \frac{N_{sel}}{N_{gen}}, \quad (1)$$

where N_{sel} is the number of selected events and N_{gen} is the total number of simulated 3π events.

The detection efficiency depends on the production mechanism of the final state. Within the Vector Meson Dominance model, the $\omega(782)$ meson decays via an intermediate $\rho\pi$ state. This mechanism was implemented in the CMD3SIM software package, developed based on the GEANT4 framework, to simulate the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process. The simulation also incorporated ISR effects to accurately reproduce the energy dependence of the detection efficiency.

The detection efficiency is $\varepsilon_{3\pi} \approx 10\%$ in the $\rho\text{-}\omega$ energy region, as shown in Fig. 9.

FIG. 9: (Color online) Energy dependence of the detection efficiency $\varepsilon_{3\pi}$ for $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$.

3.3. Background subtraction & Signal events

As mentioned above, the dominant background sources for the process under study are the reactions $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-(\gamma)$, $e^+e^- \rightarrow e^+e^-(\gamma)$, and $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-(\gamma)$. While these processes are significantly suppressed

by the acollinearity angle cut (Section 3.3.1 criterion 5, Fig. 8), however a small fraction of background events survive after the selection cuts. The background subtraction is achieved using the missing mass method. For each event, the missing mass squared M_{miss}^2 is calculated under the hypothesis that the detected charged particles are pions, using energy-momentum conservation:

$$M_{\text{miss}}^2 = E_{\text{miss}}^2 - \vec{P}_{\text{miss}}^2, \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{P}_{\text{miss}} = \vec{P}_{\pi^+} + \vec{P}_{\pi^-}, \quad (3)$$

$$E_{\text{miss}} = 2E_{\text{beam}} - E_{\pi^+} - E_{\pi^-}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{with } E_{\pi^\pm} = \sqrt{|\vec{P}_{\pi^\pm}|^2 + m_{\pi^\pm}^2} \quad (5)$$

where E_{beam} is the beam energy, and m_{π^\pm} is the charged pion mass.

The squared missing mass distribution for signal events ($e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$) has a peak at $M_{\text{miss}}^2 \approx m_{\pi^0}^2$, while background processes exhibit distinct distributions:

- $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-(\gamma)$ and $e^+e^- \rightarrow e^+e^-(\gamma)$ peak near $M_{\text{miss}}^2 = 0$
- $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-(\gamma)$ populates the negative M_{miss}^2 region

The analysis proceeds through three main stages as described below.

1. Signal shape parametrization:

The signal shape was determined at each energy point by fitting the M_{miss}^2 distribution from simulated $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ events passing all the above-mentioned selection criteria with a sum of four Gaussian functions f_{sig} .

2. Background shape parametrization: The background processes were combined according to their cross sections:

$$f_{\text{bkg}} = \sum_i \sigma_i \cdot f_i \quad \text{for } i \in \{\pi\pi(\gamma), ee(\gamma), \mu\mu(\gamma)\} \quad (6)$$

The composite distribution was then fitted with a sum of three Gaussian functions.

3. Data fitting procedure: Experimental squared missing mass distributions in the range

$M_{\text{miss}}^2 \in [-5000, 55000]$ MeV^2/c^4 were fitted using the RooFit framework [26] with the function:

$$F(M_{\text{miss}}^2) = N_{\text{sig}} \cdot f_{\text{sig}} + N_{\text{bkg}} \cdot f_{\text{bkg}}. \quad (7)$$

Resolution differences between data and simulation were accounted for by introducing a Gaussian smearing factor δ_{res} as a free parameter for the f_{sig} function. This typically increased the width of the simulated distributions by 3–5% to describe the slightly broader experimental data. Furthermore, independent shifts were applied to the mean positions of the signal and background components: $\delta_{\text{shift}}^{\text{sig}}$ and $\delta_{\text{shift}}^{\text{bkg}}$, respectively. The absolute values of these shifts typically ranged from 100 to 1200 MeV^2/c^4 , which is small compared to the nominal peak position of the squared missing mass distribution at $m_{\pi^0}^2 = 18225 \text{MeV}^2/c^4$.

The model fit thus had five free parameters:

- N_{sig} – number of signal events,
- N_{bkg} – number of background events,
- δ_{res} – resolution scaling factor,
- $\delta_{\text{shift}}^{\text{sig}}$ – signal shift,
- $\delta_{\text{shift}}^{\text{bkg}}$ – background shift.

The result of approximation is shown in Fig. 10.

The numbers of signal events after background subtraction N_{sig} and estimated background events N_{bkg} for the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ are listed in Table 2 in Section 4.

3.4. Trigger efficiency correction

The CMD-3 detector at the VEPP-2000 collider implements a trigger system with separate charged and neutral particle triggers. The charged trigger (CT) processes signals exclusively from the drift chamber tracking system, while

FIG. 10: The fitting of M_{miss}^2 distribution at $E_{\text{beam}} = 391.5 \text{ MeV}$ (logarithmic scale). Black dots represent experimental data, the model fit corresponds to the red curve, the signal component is a green color, and the background is a blue color. The pull distribution is shown in the lower panel.

the neutral trigger (NT) utilizes information from an electromagnetic calorimeter system. These independent trigger systems provide complementary event selection capabilities for different final states.

The total trigger efficiency $\varepsilon_{\text{trig}}$ is calculated accounting for the logical OR condition of the trigger system - an event is recorded if either CT, NT, or both triggers fire. This leads to the combined efficiency expression:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{trig}} = 1 - (1 - \varepsilon_{\text{CT}})(1 - \varepsilon_{\text{NT}}), \quad (8)$$

where ε_{CT} and ε_{NT} represent the individual efficiencies of charged and neutral triggers, respectively.

The individual trigger efficiencies are determined from experimental data with following expressions:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{CT}} = \frac{N_{\text{NC}}}{N_{\text{N}} + N_{\text{NC}}}, \quad \varepsilon_{\text{NT}} = \frac{N_{\text{NC}}}{N_{\text{C}} + N_{\text{NC}}}, \quad (9)$$

where

- N_{NC} counts events where both triggers fire independently
- N_N counts events triggering only the neutral system
- N_C counts events triggering only the charged system

The trigger efficiency correction is then defined as:

$$\delta_{\text{trig}} = \varepsilon_{\text{trig}} - 1. \quad (10)$$

Detailed studies of the CMD-3 trigger performance demonstrate remarkable reliability, with average efficiencies exceeding 99.9% for typical physics processes. Consequently, the associated correction $|\delta_{\text{trig}}| < 0.1\%$ is negligible and therefore omitted in analysis.

3.5. Track reconstruction efficiency correction

Analysis of experimental data revealed a minor fraction of events where a track geometrically expected within the sensitive volume of the drift chamber was not reconstructed. The MC simulation does not fully account for all detector response details, leading for example to an incomplete description of track loss effects. This discrepancy necessitates an energy-dependent correction factor $\delta_{\text{track}}(E)$ to account for differences between data and MC track reconstruction efficiencies. The correction was derived by comparing one-track and two-track event samples with simultaneously reconstructed π^0 . The purity of the sample is provided by the following requirements:

- At least two photons with $E_\gamma > 50$ MeV
- Both photons in the barrel part of calorimeter $\theta_\gamma \in [0.84, \pi - 0.84]$ rad
- Invariant mass of best photon pair $|M_{\gamma\gamma} - m_{\pi^0}| < 15$ MeV/ c^2

- Charged tracks constrained to the fiducial volume $\theta \in [1, \pi - 1]$ rad
- Cut on ionization energy loss in the drift chamber ($dE/dx \leq 6000$ a.u.).

It should be noted that the cut on dE/dx excludes events with protons produced in the interaction of beam electrons with nuclei of residual gas inside the collider ring.

The correction was defined in each energy point as

$$\delta_{\text{track}}^\pm(s) = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{data}}^\pm(s)}{\varepsilon_{\text{MC}}^\pm(s)}, \quad (11)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\text{data}}^\pm(s)$ is the detection efficiency of positive/negative charged tracks determined from the experimental sample using the expression

$$\varepsilon_{\text{data}}^\pm = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_{1tr}^\pm}{N_{2tr}}}, \quad (12)$$

and N_{1tr}^\pm is the number of events with one positive or negative charged track, N_{2tr} is the number of events with two charged tracks.

Finally, the same approach has been applied to the Monte-Carlo simulation sample to determine the track reconstruction efficiency correction $\delta_{\text{track}}^\pm(s)$ which was found to be 0.2% on average.

3.6. Systematic uncertainties

A summary of the systematic uncertainty contributions to the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ cross section measurement is presented in Table 1.

The dominant systematic uncertainty affecting the final precision of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ cross section measurement stems from the integrated luminosity determination. The luminosity was measured using large-angle Bhabha scattering and two-photon annihilation processes [27]. Since these processes are reconstructed in entirely independent detector subsystems, their simultaneous use enables continuous monitoring and control

Table 1: Systematic uncertainty contributions to the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ cross section measurement

Uncertainty Source	Contribution (%)
Luminosity measurement	1.5
Background subtraction	0.3 (OMPHI2018) 0.6 (SCAN2018)
Applying selection criteria	0.4
Polar angle reconstruction	0.3
Cross section for ISR in MC	0.3
Model uncertainty	0.3
Beam energy spread	0.2
Track reconstruction efficiency correction	0.2
Energy measurement systematic	0.1
Trigger efficiency correction	< 0.1
Total uncertainty	1.7 (OMPHI2018) 1.8 (SCAN2018)

of systematic uncertainties in the luminosity measurement, achieving an accuracy of 1.5%.

The overall systematic uncertainty from background subtraction is 0.3% for the OMPHI2018 energy points and 0.6% for the SCAN2018 dataset. This uncertainty was determined by comparing two independent analysis methods: the default physical model described in Section 3.3.3 and an alternative approach that includes an additional uniform background component N_{uniform} in Eq. (7) to account for possible beam-induced backgrounds.

The variations in the selection criteria contribute a systematic uncertainty of 0.4%. The main source is average normalized momentum cut.

The polar angle reconstruction, which influences the determination of the fiducial volume, accounts for the second-largest contribution at 0.3%. This was estimated by varying the selection criterion on θ within the systematic uncertainty of polar angle determination [9].

The simulation takes into account the radiation from the initial state. The difference in the Born cross section when using different input experimental data on the cross section measurement (e.g., from BaBar, CMD-3) in the MC event generator amounts to 0.3%.

The main model uncertainty is associated with the theoretical parameterization of the Born cross section used in the radiative correction procedure. To estimate it, corrections calculated using a Vector Dominance Model parameterization were compared with those obtained in a model-independent way [28]. The difference of 0.3% is taken as the model uncertainty. An additional check of the final state production mechanism in the generator, performed by comparing with a pure phase-space simulation, showed a negligible effect on the efficiency. Thus, the total model uncertainty is 0.3%.

The VEPP-2000 collider beam energy has a spread on the order of 250 keV per beam, which is monitored during data taking. Since the beam energy spread is not perfectly stable during data collection, its impact on the Born cross section was evaluated. By comparing cross sections obtained with different assumed values of the beam energy spread, the associated systematic uncertainty was determined not to exceed 0.2%.

The tracking efficiency correction contributes a 0.2% systematic uncertainty, estimated from the data-MC inconsistency in reconstructing tracks.

The systematic uncertainty in the absolute beam energy measurement is approximately 50

keV. While this does not directly affect the measured cross section value, it introduces a shift across the entire energy scale. However, when calculating the contribution to the AMM, the cross section is convolved with the vacuum polarization kernel Eq. (17). Due to the non-uniformity of these functions, an overall energy shift can lead to a difference in the calculated contribution. To estimate the influence of a systematic energy shift on the AMM contribution, we performed the calculation using the shifted energy scale. The resulting systematic uncertainty on the AMM contribution was found to be a bit less than 0.1%.

The trigger efficiency correction contributes less than 0.1% systematic uncertainty, estimated

from the data-MC inconsistency.

In summary, the total systematic uncertainty is 1.7% for the OMPHI2018 dataset and 1.8% for the SCAN2018 dataset. When excluding the luminosity uncertainty, which is common to all measurements, the combined systematic uncertainty becomes 0.8% for OMPHI2018 and 0.9% for SCAN2018.

4. Cross-section

The visible cross section of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process is calculated according to the formula:

$$\sigma_{vis}(s) = \frac{N_{sig}(s)}{L(s) \cdot \varepsilon_{3\pi}(s) \cdot (1 + \delta_{trig}(s)) \cdot (1 - \delta_{track}^+(s)) \cdot (1 - \delta_{track}^-(s))}, \quad (13)$$

where N_{sig} is the number of 3π events after background subtraction, $L(s)$ is the integral luminosity, δ_{trig} is the trigger efficiency correction (see Section 3.3.4), and δ_{track} track reconstruction efficiency correction (see Section 3.3.5).

The Born cross section σ_B is constructed from the visible cross section, taking into account the correction due to the initial state radiation δ_{rad} as follows:

$$\sigma_B(s) = \frac{\sigma_{vis}(s)}{1 + \delta_{rad}(s)}. \quad (14)$$

The radiative corrections, calculated using an iterative method according to [28, 29] are shown in Fig. 11. The calculation takes into account the beam energy spread of $\sigma_E \sim 250$ keV.

The obtained visible and Born cross sections are given in Table 2.

Fig. 12 presents a comparative analysis of the Born cross section measurements to previous measurements as functions of energy. The CMD-3 results from this work are used as the reference

FIG. 11: The dependence of the radiative correction on the center-of-mass energy.

baseline, with deviations from other experiments shown relative to this dataset. The dashed lines represent the total uncertainties of the CMD-3 measurement. The percentage deviation between experimental results is calculated using

the expression:

$$\text{Deviation}(\%) = 100 \times \frac{\sigma_B^{\text{exp}} - \sigma_B^{\text{CMD-3}}}{\sigma_B^{\text{CMD-3}}}, \quad (15)$$

where σ_B^{exp} is the Born cross section measurement from comparison experiments and $\sigma_B^{\text{CMD-3}}$ is the corresponding value obtained from linear interpolation of the CMD-3 data at each energy point. This interpolation was performed using a linear algorithm from the ROOT Math library in the energy range from 0.76 to 0.798 GeV.

In the energy region corresponding to the $\omega(782)$ peak, the CMD-3 measurement shows strong agreement with the SND cross section with deviations less than 2%. The Belle II cross section measurements are approximately 5% higher than the CMD-3 reference values in this region, while the BaBar result there is 3.5% lower. The most significant discrepancy is observed with the CMD-2 experiment, where the differences reach up to 10% compared to the CMD-3 cross section

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5. Contribution to muon AMM

The SM prediction of the AMM muon is determined by summing the contributions from all sectors of the SM and written as (see [30])

$$a_\mu = a_\mu^{\text{QED}} + a_\mu^{\text{EW}} + a_\mu^{\text{HVP}} + a_\mu^{\text{LbL}}, \quad (16)$$

where a_μ^{QED} are contributions to the muon AMM from electromagnetic interaction, a_μ^{EW} electroweak contributions, a_μ^{HVP} are hadronic vacuum polarization contributions, and a_μ^{LbL} are hadronic light-by-light scattering contributions. The theoretical accuracy of a_μ is almost completely limited by the leading-order of hadronic contribution, which is calculated using the measured total hadronic cross section via the dispersion integral as

$$a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}} = \frac{\alpha^2}{3\pi^2} \int_{m_\pi^2}^{\infty} \frac{K(s)R(s)}{s} ds, \quad (17)$$

measurements for the energy region near $\omega(782)$ peak.

FIG. 12: The Born cross section of the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ in the $\omega(782)$ -meson resonance region. Comparison of measurements from CMD-3 (this work) with results from SND, CMD-2, BaBar, and Belle II experiments.

where α is the fine-structure constant, m_π is the pion mass, s is the center-of-mass energy squared, $K(s)$ is the QED kernel function which is monotonously decreasing with increasing s (see [8]) and $R(s)$ is the hadronic R -ratio defined as

$$R(s) = \frac{\sigma^0(e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons})}{4\pi\alpha^2/(3s)}, \quad (18)$$

where $\sigma^0(s)$ denotes the bare cross section excluding vacuum polarization effects.

The bare cross section σ^0 can be calculated from Born cross section (σ_B) by subtracting the vacuum polarization effects.

$$\sigma^0(s) = \sigma_B |1 - \Pi(s)|^2, \quad (19)$$

where $\Pi(s)$ is the vacuum polarization operator [31].

The $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ contribution of $(a_\mu^{3\pi})$ to $a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}$ is evaluated according to the following equation:

$$a_\mu^{3\pi} = \frac{1}{4\pi^3} \int_{m_\pi^2}^{\infty} K(s)\sigma_B(s) |1 - \Pi(s)|^2 ds. \quad (20)$$

Table 2: Measured visible and Born cross sections for the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ process, integrated luminosity, radiative correction factors (δ_{rad}), signal and background event yields, and scan labels. All quantities are given with their statistical uncertainties.

\sqrt{s} (MeV)	\mathcal{L} (nb $^{-1}$)	N_{sig}	$N_{\text{phys_bkg}}$	σ_{vis} (nb)	δ_{rad}	σ_{B} (nb)	Scan label
760.02 ± 0.25	161.79 ± 0.44	713 ± 82	217 ± 79	43.71 ± 1.64	-0.172	52.80 ± 1.99	SCAN2018
763.82 ± 0.25	151.15 ± 0.44	945 ± 35	197 ± 21	59.17 ± 1.99	-0.182	72.30 ± 2.43	SCAN2018
767.79 ± 0.37	216.75 ± 0.51	2116 ± 47	287 ± 19	94.89 ± 2.09	-0.192	117.46 ± 2.59	SCAN2018
771.83 ± 0.24	195.14 ± 0.49	3159 ± 78	390 ± 57	164.47 ± 3.08	-0.207	207.33 ± 3.89	SCAN2018
773.79 ± 0.26	142.94 ± 0.42	3368 ± 80	207 ± 58	240.10 ± 4.29	-0.214	305.52 ± 5.46	SCAN2018
775.09 ± 0.24	126.01 ± 0.39	3925 ± 99	119 ± 29	314.29 ± 5.34	-0.219	402.67 ± 6.84	SCAN2018
776.03 ± 0.24	169.36 ± 0.46	6273 ± 90	255 ± 46	375.21 ± 5.11	-0.223	483.00 ± 6.58	SCAN2018
776.94 ± 0.28	124.74 ± 0.39	5690 ± 108	390 ± 80	457.66 ± 6.47	-0.226	591.40 ± 8.37	SCAN2018
777.93 ± 0.31	1255.25 ± 1.24	73049 ± 273	1295 ± 53	583.23 ± 2.35	-0.229	756.60 ± 3.05	OMPFI2018
778.02 ± 0.26	199.36 ± 0.49	11893 ± 122	196 ± 57	604.50 ± 6.05	-0.230	785.14 ± 7.86	SCAN2018
779.03 ± 0.25	170.72 ± 0.46	12568 ± 118	260 ± 39	748.45 ± 7.34	-0.233	975.47 ± 9.57	SCAN2018
779.98 ± 0.26	159.40 ± 0.44	14923 ± 135	187 ± 59	946.07 ± 8.55	-0.233	1233.93 ± 11.15	SCAN2018
780.94 ± 0.22	151.29 ± 0.43	16944 ± 138	129 ± 49	1124.83 ± 9.67	-0.230	1461.52 ± 12.57	SCAN2018
780.99 ± 0.32	3663.06 ± 2.13	413608 ± 645	4154 ± 85	1132.51 ± 1.97	-0.231	1472.93 ± 2.56	OMPFI2018
781.89 ± 0.23	150.99 ± 0.43	19126 ± 142	160 ± 34	1268.28 ± 10.28	-0.222	1630.62 ± 13.22	SCAN2018
782.73 ± 0.33	4997.98 ± 2.49	646166 ± 807	5060 ± 99	1299.24 ± 1.83	-0.211	1646.93 ± 2.31	OMPFI2018
782.80 ± 0.26	212.23 ± 0.51	27709 ± 187	238 ± 87	1309.56 ± 8.86	-0.208	1653.47 ± 11.19	SCAN2018
783.98 ± 0.26	153.75 ± 0.44	18613 ± 126	168 ± 20	1221.00 ± 10.06	-0.178	1486.55 ± 12.25	SCAN2018
784.99 ± 0.33	3981.19 ± 2.23	416999 ± 648	3965 ± 86	1054.21 ± 1.82	-0.147	1235.93 ± 2.14	OMPFI2018
785.02 ± 0.26	195.47 ± 0.49	20419 ± 192	318 ± 130	1051.75 ± 8.18	-0.146	1231.21 ± 9.58	SCAN2018
786.09 ± 0.25	210.06 ± 0.51	18355 ± 136	206 ± 22	879.58 ± 7.13	-0.109	986.80 ± 8.00	SCAN2018
788.01 ± 0.29	205.07 ± 0.51	12660 ± 119	183 ± 40	626.30 ± 6.04	-0.039	651.58 ± 6.28	SCAN2018
790.11 ± 0.27	203.06 ± 0.51	8702 ± 96	131 ± 28	442.02 ± 5.10	0.036	426.76 ± 4.92	SCAN2018
791.83 ± 0.33	602.09 ± 0.87	20749 ± 145	572 ± 30	350.43 ± 2.63	0.081	324.09 ± 2.40	OMPFI2018
792.08 ± 0.28	202.79 ± 0.51	6449 ± 87	174 ± 35	332.76 ± 4.50	0.102	301.91 ± 4.09	SCAN2018
796.05 ± 0.28	212.60 ± 0.52	4531 ± 70	159 ± 24	220.99 ± 3.57	0.221	181.01 ± 2.92	SCAN2018
797.94 ± 0.26	157.84 ± 0.45	2965 ± 56	48 ± 14	195.62 ± 3.80	0.270	154.01 ± 2.99	SCAN2018

Finally, integrating over the linear interpolation of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ cross section measured by CMD-3 detector from 0.76 to 0.798 GeV yields

$$a_{\mu}^{3\pi} = (30.94 \pm 0.06 \pm 0.28 \pm 0.46) \times 10^{-10}. \quad (21)$$

where the first uncertainty is statistical, the second is the sum of systematic uncertainties not related to luminosity, and the third is the systematic uncertainty from the luminosity measurement.

6. Summary

This paper reports a high-precision measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ Born cross section in the $\omega(782)$ resonance region ($\sqrt{s} = 760 - 798$ MeV) performed with the CMD-3 detector at the VEPP-2000 collider. The analysis is based on datasets with an integrated luminosity of 18.4 pb $^{-1}$, collected during dedicated scans in 2018, and yields a sample of approximately 2.2×10^6 selected signal events. The analysis strategy, which is solely based on charged-track reconstruction, combines effective background suppression and high signal efficiency.

The achieved precision is underscored by a total systematic uncertainty of the cross section measurement of approximately 2%. A detailed comparative analysis with previous experiments reveals a strong agreement with the SND results near the $\omega(782)$ resonance peak with deviations remaining within 2%. Notable discrepancies are observed with other major experiments: Belle II measurements are approximately 4% higher, BaBar is 3.5% lower, and the most significant difference, up to 10%, is found with the earlier CMD-2 results in the $\omega(782)$ peak region.

The observed tensions between different experimental results underscore the necessity for continued high-precision measurements at the sub-percent level.

Integrating the measured cross section, the leading-order hadronic vacuum polarization contribution to the muon anomalous magnetic moment from the 3π channel in this energy range was determined:

$$a_\mu^{3\pi} = (30.94 \pm 0.06_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.28_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.46_{\text{lum. syst.}}) \times 10^{-10}. \quad (22)$$

A primary focus for future improvement is the reduction of the dominant systematic uncertainty from the integrated luminosity determination. Since its current contribution remains the main limiting factor for improving the precision of the $a_\mu^{3\pi}$ determination.

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References

- [1] R. Oerter. *The Theory of Almost Everything: The Standard Model, the Unsung Triumph of Modern Physics*. Penguin Publishing Group, 2006.
- [2] Luigi Di Lella and Carlo Rubbia. The discovery of the W and Z particles. *Adv. Ser. Direct. High Energy Phys.*, 23:137–163, 2015.
- [3] G. Aad. Observation of a new particle in the search for the standard model Higgs boson with the ATLAS detector at the LHC. *Phys. Lett. B.*, 716(1):1–29, 2012.
- [4] Serguei Chatrchyan et al. Observation of a new boson at a mass of 125 GeV with the CMS experiment at the LHC. *Phys. Lett. B.*, 716:30–61, 2012.
- [5] J D Vergados. *The Standard Model and Beyond*. World Scientific, 2017.
- [6] B. Abi et al. Measurement of the positive muon anomalous magnetic moment to 0.46 ppm. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 126:141801, 2021.
- [7] D. P. Aguillard et al. Measurement of the positive muon anomalous magnetic moment to 0.20 ppm. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 131:161802, 2023.
- [8] T. Aoyama et al. The anomalous magnetic moment of the muon in the standard model. *Physics Reports*, 887:1–166, 2020. The anomalous magnetic moment of the muon in the Standard Model.
- [9] F. V. Ignatov et al. Measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ cross section from threshold to 1.2 GeV with the CMD-3 detector. *Phys. Rev. D*, 109:112002, 2024.
- [10] F. V. Ignatov et al. Measurement of the pion form factor with CMD-3 detector and its implication to the hadronic contribution to muon ($g - 2$). *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 132:231903, 2024.

- [11] A. Boccaletti et al. High precision calculation of the hadronic vacuum polarisation contribution to the muon anomaly, 2024.
- [12] Alexei Bazavov et al. Hadronic vacuum polarization for the muon $g-2$ from lattice QCD: Long-distance and full light-quark connected contribution. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 135:011901, Jul 2025.
- [13] R. Aliberti et al. The anomalous magnetic moment of the muon in the standard model: an update, 2025.
- [14] D. P. Aguillard et al. Measurement of the positive muon anomalous magnetic moment to 127 ppb, 2025.
- [15] M. N. Achasov et al. Study of the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ in the energy region \sqrt{s} below 0.98 GeV. *Phys. Rev. D*, 68:052006, 2003.
- [16] R. R. Akhmetshin et al. Reanalysis of hadronic cross-section measurements at CMD-2. *Phys. Lett. B*, 578:285–289, 2004.
- [17] J.P. Lees et al. Study of the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ using initial state radiation with babar. *Physical Review D*, 104:112003, 2021.
- [18] M. Ablikim et al. Measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ cross section from 0.7 GeV to 3.0 GeV via initial-state radiation, 2019.
- [19] I. Adachi et al. Measurement of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ cross section in the energy range 0.62–3.50 GeV at Belle II. *Phys. Rev. D*, 110:112005, Dec 2024.
- [20] Dmitry Shwartz et al. Recommissioning and Perspectives of VEPP-2000 e^+e^- Collider. *PoS, ICHEP2016:054*, 2017.
- [21] I. Logashenko et al. CMD-3 overview. *EPJ Web of Conferences*, 218:02001, 01 2019.
- [22] F. Grancagnolo et al. Drift chamber for the CMD-3 detector. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A*, 623:114–116, 2010.
- [23] Alexey V. Bragin, Lev M. Barkov, Sergey V. Karpov, Victor S. Okhapkin, Yuri S. Popov, Alexander A. Ruban, and Vladimir P. Smakhtin. Test results of the thin superconducting solenoid for the CMD-3 detector. *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, 18(2):399–402, 2008.
- [24] V.E. Shebalin et al. Calorimetry of the CMD-3 detector. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 824:710–712, 2016. Frontier Detectors for Frontier Physics: Proceedings of the 13th Pisa Meeting on Advanced Detectors.
- [25] A. A. Korobov, B. A. Shwartz, and A. I. Vorobiov. CMD-3 muon system efficiency. *J. Instrum.*, 15(10):C10018, oct 2020.
- [26] Rene Brun and Fons Rademakers. ROOT - An Object Oriented Data Analysis Framework. *Nucl. Inst. & Meth. in Phys. Res.*, A 389:81–86, 1997.
- [27] A. E. Ryzhenenkov et al. Current status of luminosity measurement with the CMD-3 detector at the VEPP-2000 collider. *EPJ Web Conf.*, 212:04011, 2019.
- [28] S. S. Gribov and A. S. Popov. A new method for obtaining a Born cross section using visible cross section data from e^+e^- colliders. *JHEP*, 11:203, 2021.
- [29] E. A. Kuraev and Victor S. Fadin. On Radiative Corrections to e^+e^- Single Photon Annihilation at High-Energy. *Sov. J. Nucl. Phys.*, 41:466–472, 1985.
- [30] Alexander Keshavarzi, Daisuke Nomura, and Thomas Teubner. $g-2$ of charged leptons, $\alpha(M_Z^2)$, and the hyperfine splitting of muonium. *Phys. Rev. D*, 101:014029, Jan 2020.
- [31] F. Ignatov. Vacuum polarization. <https://cmd.inp.nsk.su/~ignatov/vpl/>.